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IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF THE PERIOD OF FATTENING OF LIVESTOCK AND MAIN ASPECTS OF PAYING ATTENTION TO THEM.

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Annotation: The period of livestock fattening and the main aspects of paying attention to them play an important role in the process of raising and effectively feeding and managing livestock in agriculture. During this period, aspects related to the health of livestock, improvement of breeding quality and technologies of their care should be taken into account. In the process of fattening, factors such as preservation and development of genetic resources of animals, as well as methods of prevention and treatment of diseases, communication and fodder, water supply are important. In this article, we will talk about the main aspects that need to be paid attention to in the process of fattening livestock, what needs to be done to increase their economic efficiency and sustainable development.

Key words: breeding, fattening, Kluwer - Strauch method, cattle breeding, Frowein method, measuring the live weight of cattle, building a barn.

Enter. The main goal of cattle fattening is to achieve the highest efficiency. To benefit from fattening, cattle should be treated and vaccinated against parasites, body weight should be checked regularly, groups should be separated and fed according to body weight, and feed should be fed with high energy and protein (protein) feed. Regular fattening of livestock with feed available on the farm is not always effective. This way of fattening can remain only in the form of labor cost and profit from feed for the cattle breeder.

The main part. A livestock farmer should consider the following aspects before starting fattening for economic efficiency and profit:

Family members who take care of livestock must undergo annual medical examinations and receive vaccinations against infectious diseases (to prevent the disease from being transmitted from animals to humans).

The main condition for the care of livestock is their timely and continuous feeding (during the period of care in the nursery, cattle are fed with feed prepared in the summer). One of the second important conditions is necessary hygienic care. This is of great importance in maintaining the live weight of the animal.

When raising cattle, first of all, attention should be paid to the purpose for which the cattle are raised. If it is raised for milk, its diet should include chopped blue grass, hay, beets, and high-quality concentrate feed. If the cattle are being fed in the ration, there must be a large amount of concentrate (bran, fodder, meal, etc.) in their diet. Livestock should be in a state of low movement.

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Cattle storage rooms, i.e. barns, should be spacious, light and have frames for air exchange. The barn must be well maintained, the walls and manger must be disinfected with lime, and all holes must be closed. The manger should be well ventilated, urine can flow. If possible, it is necessary to clean and store the goods every day, if not, when they are dirty. For this purpose, a scraper is used.

It is necessary to follow the rules when building a farm. The length of the pen for cows should not be less than 170-200 cm, and the width should not be less than 140-160 cm. The manger will be lower - cattle should be fed with their neck bent, but not stretched. The manger should be made oval, preferably not rectangular, that is, the width of the top is eighty centimeters and the bottom is not less than fifty centimeters. It should not be large enough to accommodate one-time feeding, and it is better to be in front of the water of the cattle being fed.

Cattle for fattening should be selected based on their breed, age, body weight, body structure and breed. That is, it is necessary to buy cattle that are best suited for fattening.

Sufficient coarse and concentrated feeds must be stocked and these feeds must be of good quality and properly stored.

Livestock feed should be given on the basis of norms and rations, feed with high energy and protein. It is necessary for the breeder to create balanced rations in feeding.

Before feeding, livestock should be weighed, divided into groups based on body weight and fed according to body weight.

During the fattening period, the live weight of livestock is measured once a month on a scale or, if it is not possible to weigh on a scale, the oblique length of the body and chest circumference, behind the shoulder bones are measured with a tape measure. is increased. The live weight of older cattle is also determined by the Kluwer-Strauch method. For this, measurements of chest circumference and oblique length of the body are taken.

Then the live weight is determined using specially developed tables.

Then the live weight is determined with the help of specially developed tables. The numbers given in the table are set for cattle of medium fatness. Therefore, depending on whether the cattle are fat or thin, their weight is increased by 5-10% using the table. The weight of cattle with moderate to low obesity is reduced by 5-10%.

Determination of live weight of cattle. The live weight of young cattle is determined by the Frowein method. In this method, the measurements of the breast circumference and oblique length of the body of cattle are taken, and the live weight is found using the indicators in special tables (Table 1).

Determining the live weight of cattle by the Kluwer - Strauch method

Chest circumference behind the shoulder	Slant length of the body, sm														
	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90	95

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blades, sm																		
25	1	64																
30	1	80	87															
35	1	96	03	13														
40	1	16	23	31	41													
45	1	32	40	50	59	69												
50	1	47	56	66	77	86	96											
55	1	64	74	85	95	96	17	28										
60	1	82	90	01	13	24	34	47	50									
65	1		10	23	34	47	58	70	81	94								
70	1			42	55	68	80	98	04	17	31							
75	1				74	90	03	17	29	43	57	70						
80	1					14	28	43	52	71	86	00	15					
85	1						49	64	78	94	08	24	40	52				
90	1							92	06	22	38	55	72	85	02			
95	1								31	49	66	82	00	15	29	48		
00	2									80	97	14	34	49	67	84		
05	2										26	44	62	80	90	17		
10	2											78	99	16	36	54		

When feeding livestock, it is necessary to calculate when to run out of feed, or in terms of time, or best of all, based on the body weight of the animal. In other words, shortening the period of feeding should not prolong the period of fattening.

Conclusion. Livestock fattening, that is, their improvement and development, is an important part of agriculture. This process is important not only for improving livestock productivity, but also for ensuring food security, economic development and improving the social welfare of rural areas. In addition, to increase the knowledge of the villagers on livestock breeding, to introduce them to modern technologies, to implement the programs adopted by the state for the development of livestock breeding, to provide subsidies and other support, to introduce innovative technologies in the process of animal fattening, for example, it is important to improve the results by using genetic modification or new diets.

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